

Conversion of lapachol to array of furano and pyranonaphthoquinone congeners^ψ

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Chemical conversion of lapachol to α -lapachone, β -lapachone, dehydro- α -lapachone, dehydroiso- α -lapachone and dehydroiso- β -lapachone by reaction with aqueous NaNO_2 and glacial AcOH ; rhinacanthin-A, stenocarpoquinone-A, stenocarpoquinone-B and its isomer by reaction with *meta*-chloroperbenzoic acid at 0° for 30 min and dehydro- α -lapachone and dehydro- β -lapachone at 25° for 4 h respectively and di- and tribromo derivatives by reaction with Br_2 in chloroform has been reviewed. In most of these reactions prenyl chain cyclises into an oxygen function to give a number of furano and pyranonaphthoquinone derivatives. Some of these naphthoquinones co-occur with lapachol in the same plant species.

Lapachol **1**, a naturally occurring 2-hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone, occurs in sufficient quantity in the woods of various plants of Bignoniaceae and Verbenaceae. It has been isolated as shining yellow needles, m.p. 139–140° in our laboratory from the heartwoods and barks of *Tecomella undulata*^{1–3}, *Phyllanthron comorense*^{4,5}, *Tabebuia rosea*^{6,7}, *Heterophragma adenophyllum*⁸, *Markhamia stipulata*^{9,10}, *M. platycalyx*¹¹ (Bignoniaceae) and *Tectona grandis*¹² (Verbenaceae). Earlier it has also been isolated by many workers¹³. In certain plants it is present to such an extent that it is clearly visible in the form of yellow powder in the coarsely powdered heartwood shavings. Lapachol has been widely used in dyeing industry, and it possesses several biological properties. It showed antitumour¹⁴, antiviral¹⁵, antimalarial¹⁶ and anti-inflammatory¹⁷ activities. It has also been studied for acid-base indicator property¹⁸.

Literature survey has revealed that a number of cyclization reactions of lapachol have been studied in detail¹³. The main striking feature of the chemistry of lapachol is the ease with which the prenyl chain cyclizes into an oxygen function to give an array of furano and pyrano derivatives, some of which occur naturally. In pursuing our interest in chemical transformation reactions we have carried out the conversion of lapachol to dehydroiso- α -lapachone **2**, dehydroiso- β -lapachone **3** along with α -lapachone **4**, β -lapachone **5** and dehydro- α -lapachone **6** by reaction with aqueous NaNO_2 and glacial AcOH ¹⁹ (Scheme 1).

When lapachol **1** was allowed to react with aqueous NaNO_2 and glacial AcOH a pair of dihydrofuranonaphthoquinones **2** and **3** and a pair of dihydropyranonaphthoquinones **4** and **5** were obtained in addition to dehydro- α -lapachone **6**.

Scheme 1

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

The formation of α - and β -lapachones (4 and 5) can be rationalized by considering the decomposition of nitrous acid to nitric acid under refluxing condition and latter transformed lapachol into α - and β -lapachones in equal quantity for which there is precedent¹³. The formation of sodium acetate during reaction and subsequent abstraction of one of the methylene protons by the nucleophilic attack of acetate ion resulted in the formation of dehydro- α -lapachone¹³ 6. The compounds 2 and 3 were obtained in major amount and their formation was catalysed by acetic acid

The addition of acetic acid to olefinic double bond of the side chain is followed by removal of one of the methylene hydrogens as hydride ion leading to cyclization to the five membered ring which on elimination of AcOH gave compounds 2 and 3 (Scheme 2).

When lapachol 1 was allowed to react with *meta*-chloroperbenzoic acid in methylene chloride at 0° for 30 min a pair of dihydrofuranonaphthoquinones 7 and 8 and a pair of dihydropyranonaphthoquinones 9 and 10 were obtained²⁰ (Scheme 3).

Scheme 2. Probable mechanism of formation of products 4, 5, 6, 2 and 3.

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

The reaction appears to proceed through initial formation of tautomeric epoxides^{21,22} 11 and 12. Epoxy ring opening, followed by cyclization may then afford both five membered furanonaphthoquinones-stenocarpoquinone-B 7 and β -1-(hydroxyisoprenyl)-dihydrofuran-1,2-naphthoquinone 8 and pyranonaphthoquinones-rhinacanthin-A 9 and stenocarpoquinone-A 10 (Scheme 4).

When lapachol was allowed to react with MCPBA in methylene chloride for 4 h and 25°, dehydro- α -lapachone 6 and dehydro- β -lapachone 13 were formed²⁰. Probably these compounds were formed by dehydration of 9 and 10 which were formed initially at low temperature (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

A solution of lapachol 1 in chloroform on treatment with a solution of bromine in chloroform afforded 2-hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone 14 and 2-hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-6-bromo-1,4-naphthoquinone 15 in almost equal quantity (Scheme 6).

The characterization of products 2-15 was done on the basis of their spectral data as well as by comparison with authentic samples. Product 2 obtained as golden yellow leaflets, m.p. 102-3°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -31.00^\circ$ (CHCl₃) was characterized as dehydroiso- α -lapachone. The IR spectrum exhibited absorption bands at 1675, 1650, 1640, 1600 cm⁻¹ and UV spectrum in ethanol showed absorptions at 253, 295 and 342 nm characteristic of 1,4-naphthoquinones. The ¹H NMR spectrum when determined in CDCl₃ displayed ABX splitting pattern. A pair of AB double doublets at δ 2.94 (*J* 17, 8 Hz) and 3.21 (*J* 17, 10 Hz) and a double doublet at δ 5.38 (*J* 10, 8 Hz) corresponded to methylene and methine protons of dihydrofuran ring. A broad doublet centred at δ 5.02 assigned to vinylic protons of side chain and an olefinic me-

Scheme 6

thyl gave a singlet at δ 1.67. Aromatic region showed a set of identical multiplets at δ 7.68 and 8.07 integrated for two aromatic protons each. In mass spectrum it exhibited strong molecular ion peak at m/z 240 corresponding to its molecular composition $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$. Array of intense peaks at m/z 225, 212 and 197 in mass spectrum appeared due to the loss of methyl radical and one and two molecules of CO successively from molecular ion. It was further confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample. The 1H NMR spectrum of its isomeric compound **3**, obtained as red granules, m.p. 96° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} -25^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) was very much close to that of compound **2** except the splitting pattern in aromatic region where a multiplet at δ 7.66 integrated for three aromatic protons and another multiplet at δ 7.95 corresponding to one aromatic proton indicating the angular cyclization of side chain. The presence of an associated $[M+2]$ ion peak of comparable intensity in the mass spectrum further supports the 1,2-naphthoquinonoid nature of the compound²¹ and was characterized as dehydroiso- β -lapachone. The 1H NMR spectra of compounds **4** and **5** were very much similar to each other barring some minor difference in aromatic region. These were identified as α - and β -lapachones respectively. The 1H NMR spectrum of compound **6** showed a pair of doublets with coupling constant 10 Hz at δ 5.74 and 6.66 corresponding to olefinic protons with *cis* geometry. A singlet at δ 1.54 integrated for six protons corresponded to two geminal methyl groups. The identity of **4**, **5** and **6** was finally established with their authentic samples.

Compounds **7** and **8** showed UV spectra consistent with α - and β -lapachone systems respectively²². The 1H NMR spectrum of stenocarpoquinone-B **7** showed characteristic signal at δ 4.85 (t, J 8 Hz) assignable to C-2 methine proton whereas corresponding signal in 1,2-naphthoquinone **8** also appeared at δ 4.85 (t, J 8 Hz). Similarly for pyranonaphthoquinones **9** and **10**, 1,2- and 1,4-quinonoid systems were distinguished on the basis of their UV spectra. The 1H NMR spectrum of the rhinacanthin-A **9** displayed characteristic C-3 methine proton signal at δ 3.87 (t, J 5 Hz). It was further confirmed by comparison with 1H NMR of an authentic sample. Its molecular formula $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ was established by taking high resolution of its parent ion peak at m/z 258.0892. The C-3 methine proton signal in stenocarpoquinone-A **10** appeared at δ 3.97 (t, J 5 Hz). The formation of dehydro- α -lapachone **6** and dehydro- β -lapachone **13** was confirmed by the appearance of a pair of doublets with coupling constants 10 Hz each at δ 5.74 and 6.66 and 6.20 and 7.07 respectively in their 1H NMR spectra and by comparison with authentic specimens.

Similarly the compounds **14** and **15** were characterized as 2-hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-1,4-naphtho-

quinone and 2-hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-6-bromo-1,4-naphthoquinone respectively from their 1H NMR spectra.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded in KBr on FTIR Nicolet Magna 550 spectrometer, 1H NMR spectra in $CDCl_3$ on JEOL FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer, mass spectra on a JEOL JMS-D-300 instrument at 70 eV direct inlet; and UV spectra in ethanol (95%) on a Perkin-Elmer model 202 automatic recording spectrometer. CC was done over silica gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh) and prep. TLC over silica gel PF₂₅₄, ⁶⁰F₂₅₄ E. Merck plates. Melting points were recorded in soft glass capillaries in an electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Chemical shifts are reported in δ , ppm.

Lapachol, a yellow crystalline compound, m.p. 139 – 140° , isolated from the plant *Heterophragma adenophyllum* was used for these reactions; UV (λ_{max} EtOH) 251, 278, 333 nm; IR (nujol) 3350, 1660, 1630, 1410 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 1.73 (s, CH_3), 1.82 (s, CH_3), 3.35 (d, J 7 Hz, $-CH_2-$), 5.27 (t, J 7 Hz, $=CH$), 7.81 (m, $2 \times ArH$), 8.11 (m, $2 \times ArH$) ppm.

Reaction of lapachol with HNO_2 :

To a solution of lapachol (2.0 g, 8.3 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) in 250 ml RB flask, an aqueous solution of $NaNO_2$ (3.208 g, 46 mmol) was added and the resulting mixture was heated at 80° for 6 h with magnetic stirring. It was left overnight and then the reaction mixture was diluted and extracted with Et_2O . The ethereal solution was washed with 2% $NaHCO_3$ solution and water, respectively. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and subjected to prep. TLC on precoated glass plates giving compounds **2**–**6** along with two minor components, which could not be characterized owing to their meagre amounts.

Dehydroiso- α -lapachone 2: Golden yellow leaflets, m.p. 102 – 103° , yield 70 mg, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -31.0^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$); IR (KBr) 1675 (C=O), 1650, 1640, 1600 (C=C), 1450, 1375, 1245 cm^{-1} ; UV (EtOH) 253, 295, 342 nm; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) 1.67 (3H, s, $=C-CH_3$), 2.94 (1H, dd, J 17, 8 Hz, H-3), 3.21 (1H, dd, J 17, 10 Hz, H-3'), 5.02 (2H, dbr, $=CH_2$), 5.38 (1H, dd, J 10, 8 Hz, H-2), 7.68 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.07 (2H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) 240 $[M]^+$ ($C_{15}H_{12}O_3$) (46.2), 225 $[M-Me]^+$ (94.8), 212 $[M-CO]^+$ (92.4), 197 $[225-CO]^+$ (80.9), 183 $[225-CH_2=C=O]^+$ (17.5), 104 $[C_7H_4O]^+$ (100); 76 $[C_6H_4]^+$ (79).

Dehydroiso- β -lapachone 3: Red granules, m.p. 96° , yield 65 mg, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -25^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$); IR (KBr) 1690 (C=O), 1636, 1630, 1595 (C=C) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) 1.66 (3H,

s, =C-CH₃), 2.96 (1H, dd, *J* 18, 8 Hz, H-3), 3.23 (1H, dd, *J* 18, 10 Hz, H-3'), 5.04 (2H, dbr, =CH₂), 5.40 (1H, dd, *J* 10, 8 Hz, H-2), 7.66 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.95 (1H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) 240 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₂O₃) (52.0), 242 [M+2]⁺ (11), 225 [M-Me]⁺ (45.7), 212 [M-CO]⁺ (51), 197 [225-CO]⁺ (76.7), 183 [225-CH₂=C=O]⁺ (16.9), 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺ (90), 76 [C₆H₄]⁺ (100).

α-Lapachone 4 : Pale yellow needles, m.p. 117–118°, yield 50 mg; IR (KBr) 1678 (C=O), 1640, 1610, 1595 (C=C) cm⁻¹; UV (EtOH) 251, 282, 332, 375 nm; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) 1.47 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 1.87 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, -CH₂-), 2.72 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, -CH₂-), 7.90 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.26 (2H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) 242 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₄O₃) (100), 227 [M-Me]⁺ (50), 199 [227-CO]⁺ (60).

β-Lapachone 5 : Red needles, m.p. 154–155°, yield 40 mg; IR (KBr) 1690 (C=O), 1640, 1632, 1598 (C=C) cm⁻¹; UV (EtOH) 256, 282, 330, 431 nm; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) 1.51 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 1.87 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, -CH₂-), 2.63 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz, -CH₂-), 7.77 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.22 (1H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) 242 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₄O₃) (60), 227 [M-Me]⁺ (40), 199 [227-CO]⁺ (50), 102 (100).

Dehydro-α-lapachone 6 : Red needles, m.p. 143–144°, yield 45 mg; IR (KBr) 1681 (C=O), 1640, 1590 (C=C) cm⁻¹; UV (EtOH) 267, 276, 333, 434 nm; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) 1.54 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 5.74 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, =CH), 6.66 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, =CH), 7.82 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.10 (2H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) 240 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₂O₃) (98.8), 225 [M-Me]⁺ (96.6), 212 [M-CO]⁺ (100), 197 [225-CO]⁺ (98.4), 184 [212-CO]⁺ (35.6), 183 [225-CH₂=C=O]⁺ (57.6), 169 [197-CO]⁺ (62.6), 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺ (71.4), 76 [C₆H₄]⁺ (62.6), 50 [C₄H₂]⁺ (40).

Reaction of lapachol with meta-chloroperbenzoic acid :

To a solution of lapachol (2.4 g, 10 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (30 ml) was added a solution of meta-chloroperbenzoic acid (5.1 g, 30 mmol) in dichloromethane (50 ml) at 0°. After 30 min workup was carried out by treating the reaction mixture with a saturated aqueous sodium hydrogen sulphite (100 ml) for 20 min. The organic layer was separated, washed successively with saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate (2 × 25 ml), water (2 × 25 ml) and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The crude orange solid, 1.5 g was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel employing chloroform as solvent. The following compounds were obtained, which were further purified by preparative TLC.

Stenocarpoquinone-B 9 : Yellow needles, 0.21g, m.p. 160–161°; UV (λ_{max} EtOH) 250, 284, 331, 372 nm; IR (KBr) 3450, 1670, 1630, 1585, 1560, 1250, 1125 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR

(CDCl₃) δ 1.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.42 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.45 (sbr, OH), 3.18 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂-), 4.85 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, -CH-), 7.7 (2H, m, 2 × ArH) and 8.05 (2H, m, 2 × ArH) ppm.

β-1-(Hydroxyisoprenyl)-dehydrofurano-1,4-naphthoquinone 10 : Red needles, 0.26 g, m.p. 132°; UV (λ_{max} EtOH) 253, 280, 332, 430 nm; IR (KBr) 3460, 1690, 1630, 1590, 1565, 1250, 1125, 940, 780 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.21 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.34 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.98 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, -CH₂-), 4.85 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, -CH-), 7.55 (3H, m, 3 × ArH) and 7.90 (1H, m, 1 × ArH) ppm; MS (*m/z*) 258 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₄O₄), 240 [M⁺-H₂O], 230 [M⁺-CO], 212 [230-H₂O]⁺.

Rhinacanthin-A 11 : Orange solid, 0.1 g, m.p. 186–187°; UV (λ_{max} EtOH) 245, 251, 282, 330 nm; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.46 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.67 (1H, dd, *J* 5, 18 Hz, -CH-), 2.83 (1H, dd, *J* 5, 18 Hz, -CH-), 3.87 (1H, t, *J* 5 Hz, -CH-OH), 7.60 (2H, m, 2 × ArH) and 8.00 (2H, m, 2 × ArH) ppm; MS (*m/z*) 258 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₄O₄) (100%), 243 [M-Me]⁺ (18%), 225 (29%), 159 (29%).

Stenocarpoquinone-A 12 : Red needles, 0.6 g, m.p. 170–171°; UV (λ_{max} EtOH) 250, 282, 331, 431 nm; IR (KBr) 3450, 1690, 1650, 1590, 1565 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.50 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.61 (1H, dd, *J* 5, 18 Hz, -CH-), 2.77 (1H, dd, *J* 5, 18 Hz, -CH-), 3.97 (1H, t, *J* 5 Hz, -CH-OH), 7.5 and 7.65 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, each, 2 × ArH), 7.84 and 8.05 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz each, 2 × ArH) ppm; MS (*m/z*) 258 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₄O₄).

Reaction of lapachol with meta-chloroperbenzoic acid at 25° for 4 h :

To a solution of lapachol (1.2 g, 5 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (15 ml) was added a solution of meta-chloroperbenzoic acid (2.5 g, 15 mmol) in dichloromethane (25 ml at 25°). After 4 h work up was carried out as usual. The crude red solid, 800 mg was subjected to preparative TLC giving 300 mg of dehydro-α-lapachone 6 and 200 mg of dehydro-β-lapachone 13.

Dehydro-β-lapachone 13 : Red mass, IR (nujol) 1690, 1637, 1621, 1587 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.42 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.60 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.20 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, =CH), 7.07 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, =CH), 7.64 (3H, m, 3 × ArH), 7.86 (1H, m, 1 × ArH) ppm; MS (*m/z*) 240 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₂O₃).

Reaction of lapachol with Br₂ :

A solution of lapachol (1.5 g, 6.2 mmol) in 90 ml of CHCl₃ in a stoppered conical flask was treated with a solution of bromine in CHCl₃ (4 ml of Br₂ dissolved in 15 ml of CHCl₃) and the resulting mixture was heated for 5 min on a water-bath and kept overnight at room temperature.

The excess Br₂ and the chloroform were removed by evaporation in fuming cupboard. It was separated by preparative TLC using precoated glass plates with silica gel into compounds **14** and **15**.

2-Hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-1,4-naphthoquinone 14 : Violet red mass, yield 75 mg; IR (nujol) 1668 (C=O), 1640, 1610 (C=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.66 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.69 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.18 (1H, dd, *J* 18, 8 Hz, -CH-), 3.35 (1H, dd, *J* 18, 6 Hz, -CH-), 4.33 (1H, dd, *J* 8, 6 Hz, -CHBr), 7.89 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.17 (2H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) 400 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₄O₃Br₂).

2-Hydroxy-3-(2,3-dibromo-3-methylbutyl)-6-bromo-1,4-naphthoquinone 15 : Maroon needles, m.p. 168–169°, yield 150 mg; IR (KBr) 1670 (C=O), 1630, 1610, 1580 (C=C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.65 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 3.12 (1H, dd, *J* 17, 7 Hz, -CH-), 3.29 (1H, dd, *J* 17, 6 Hz, -CH-), 4.33 (1H, dd, *J* 6, 7 Hz, -CHBr), 7.44 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.88 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, m, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) 478 [M]⁺ (C₁₅H₁₃O₃Br₃).

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